

Evaluating the Impact of Clinical Nursing Leadership Program on Professional Competence and Leadership Skills

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Abstract

This study evaluates the impact of the clinical nursing leadership program on leadership capacity and professional skills using a registered nurse survey of 30 respondents among those who completed the Clinical Nursing Leadership Program at tertiary care hospital. Operating under a Google Form with multiple choice questions, checkboxes, and open-ended statements, the study examined leadership confidence, skills, preference of development, issues, and career goals. Results reveal high confidence (86.7% Very or Extremely confident) and strength (90%) when communicating, team-managing, and resolving problems but a gap (40%) where strategic skills such as vision and objective-setting are concerned. High marks (93.3% Good or Excellent) are given the program, yet systematic limitations prevail, especially a high workload (69%), slowing its impact. Nurses' career goals remain mid- and senior-level positions with a strong sense of the need for mentorship. It is recommended that structured mentorship and management of workload occur with strategic training. These findings reveal that the program significantly enhances leadership skills but special interventions are needed to overcome limitations and enhance career development and patient care and organizational outcomes [1].

Introduction

Nursing leadership is one of the keys to quality patient care, staff retention and organizational resilience of healthcare organizations at Prince Sultan Military Medical City. Some of the issues that healthcare systems experience and require nurse leaders to enhance the positive dynamics within the team, practices and objectives that are supported by evidence, are patient acuity, staffing problems, and resource shortages [2]. The Saudi Tertiary Care Hospital

clinical nursing leadership program will help to develop the necessary competencies to enable nurses to take up a mid-level and senior-level position, including Nurse Manager and Director of Nursing, by instilling the following essential competencies: communication, team management, problem-solving, and strategic planning. However, to gauge the effectiveness of the program in building professional competence and leadership, it is important to evaluate how well the program is working in meeting the evolving needs of

More Information

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nurses and assisting Saudi Tertiary Care Hospital in attaining its objectives of delivering high-quality healthcare. This article compares survey data of 30 nurses to determine the effect of the program on leadership confidence and competencies, development preferences, challenges, and career aspirations, and to determine the strengths, weaknesses, and improvement recommendations [3].

The **purpose** of this research is to evaluate the extent to which the clinical nursing leadership program enhances nurses' professional competence and leadership skills, focusing on their ability to lead teams, develop key competencies, and pursue career advancement. It is compared according to both quantitative (e.g. confidence levels, e.g. 86.7% reporting high confidence, program rating, e.g. 93.3% Good or Excellent) and qualitative information on what kind of development is needed (e.g. mentorship, clear career pathways) and which obstacles stand in the way (e.g. high workload, resource constraints). These perceptions taken in combination are likely to provide the full picture of the program effectiveness and its relation to career goals among nurses, in particular, the Nurse Manager (56.7% aspiration) and the Director of Nursing (40) [1].

Expected results include high levels of leadership confidence and satisfaction, reflecting the program's success in fostering interpersonal skills like Communication, Team Management, and Problem-Solving, which are critical for clinical leadership [3]. However, there are loopholes in the strategic competencies (such as Vision and Goal-Setting (mentioned by only 40%)) which is to be expected since they are necessary in high-level positions. The barriers are highly likely to be systemic, particularly the overload of work (69%), and shortage of resources (41.4%), which is not unique to healthcare in the global context [2]. Likely to be distributed in qualitative responses, the need to possess a set mentorship and a clear promotion policy is crucial to supporting a career advancement.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to strengthen Saudi Tertiary Care Hospital leadership pipeline, enhancing nurses' capacity to lead effectively and improve patient outcomes. The research will inform the desired interventions by defining the program strengths, including high-satisfaction and career alignment, and the program solutions to the challenges, including workload and mentorship gap, that will facilitate the development of high-quality nursing leadership [1]. The results will be beneficial to the organizational objectives to enhance patient safety, staff retention, and operational efficiency and will be included in the existing body of research on nursing leadership in the military and civilian medical care. The study is confined to the local context of Saudi Tertiary

Care Hospital, but valuable in practice due to these limitations, e.g. small sample size (30), no demographics [4]. These strategies will be further streamlined in future studies involving larger sample sizes with demographic information.

Methodology

The survey was conducted through Google Forms and the responses were collected among 30 nurses who completed the Clinical Nurse Leadership Program within the Nursing Affairs at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) one of the Saudi Arabia's leading tertiary care institution, as their professional email addresses (e.g., psmmc.med.sa) indicated. The questionnaire had a variety of questions of various types where they were multiple choice questions, checkbox questions and open-ended questions in four parts of Leadership Competencies, Leadership Development Opportunities, Leadership Challenges and Career Aspirations. Descriptive statistics (percentages) were applied to quantitative data via the summary features of Google Forms, and there might be an option to export it to Google Sheets and calculates additional statistics. The qualitative answers were coded in the form of themes in order to find common themes i.e. resource constraints and mentorship needs and were coded based on the thematic analysis model of [4]. The analysis presupposes that all respondents are nurses who ever took part in the leadership program; however, due to the absence of demographic information (e.g., years of experience), it is not possible to segment the population. The design of the survey generated in-depth information, yet the limitation is the small sample size (30).

Results

Leadership Competencies and Confidence

The survey assessed the effect of leadership program on the confidence and competencies of the nurses. In terms of trust in leading teams, 50% (15 respondents) indicated that they were Extremely confident, 36.7% (11) Very confident, 6.7% (2) Moderately confident, and 6.7% (2) Slightly confident with no respondents indicating Not confident at all. It shows that 86.7 percent of them express high confidence, which implies that the program has effectiveness in developing self-assessed leadership capacity [3]. The 13.4% of moderate or slight confidence can outline the areas where the program can be useful in terms of supporting more.

Communication, Team Management, Conflict Resolution, and Problem-Solving were the strongest competencies (chosen by 90% (27/30) of respondents), and the next strong competencies were Decision-Making (83.3%, 25/30) and Motivation (80 percent and 24/30). Less common were Emotional Intelligence and Delegation (60%, 18/30) and Vision and Goal-Setting (40%, 12/30). These findings indicate the power of the

program in building interpersonal and operational skills, which are vital to clinical leadership, but a gap in strategic skills such as Vision and Goal-Setting, which are needed in senior positions [1].

Figure 1: Confidence in Leading a Team

This bar chart shows the distribution of responses to “How confident do you feel in your ability to lead a team?” with 15 respondents selecting “Extremely confident” and 11 selecting “Very confident,” highlighting strong leadership confidence.

Program Effectiveness and Development Preferences
The success of the clinical nursing leadership program was measured based on survey questions that assessed the rating of program, career goal alignment, the preferred type of development, and the preferred frequency of training. This survey, filled out by 30 nurses, offers some helpful information on the effect of the program on professional development and change areas. The results demonstrate how much satisfaction and relevance they have with the opportunities to enhance mentorship and workload constraints, which is also coherent with the study on the efficient development of leadership in nursing [1].

The leadership program was rated highly with 60 or 18 out of 30 ranking it as an excellent program, 33.3 or 10 out of 30 ranking it as a good program and only 6.7 or 2 out of 30 ranking it as very poor. None of the respondents chose either Poor or Fair, which shows that the level of satisfaction was 93.3. The high approval shows that the program is effective in equipping nurses with leadership skills that are applicable in clinical environments, which may assist them in becoming more professional [3]. Likewise, 93.3% (28 of 30) said that they have career goals that the program is in line with, 6.7% (2 of 30) said Not sure and none said No. The near-match with career objectives indicates the utility of the program as per nurse objectives, particularly, Nurse Manager and Director of Nursing, which were identified in the survey

[1]. However, the fact that the percentage of the number of Very poor ratings is low and that the number of people who were not sure is also low, means that a small group of nurses may experience barriers to enjoying the program, which may be due to the personal or systemic restrictions they may have [6].

Figure 2: PSMMS Leadership Program Ratings

The types of development preferred included strong preference of hands-on, nurse specific training. The most wanted were Mentorship and Workshops (73.3% of 30, 22 out of 30), Training Tailored to Nursing (60% of 30, 18 out of 30), Peer Learning/Shadowing (56.7% or 17 out of 30) and Online Courses (33.3% or 10 out of 30) [6]. Its mentorship and workshops choices show that the program can be effective in providing desirable, context-based learning opportunities that would attract the practical requirements of the nursing leadership [1]. The fact that nurses favor face-to-face training over online training is reflective of the reality that teamwork and feedback will be conducted in a real-time environment and in a clinical setting which is likely to be justified. The shadowing gap in relation to the mentorship one means the gap in mentoring because only the practical leadership style is crucial to develop practical skills [3]. Increasing these elements might also increase the effectiveness of the program [7].

On training frequency, 66.7% (20 of 30) answered annual training, 26.7% (8 of 30) answered As needed, and the remaining 3.3% (1 of 30 each) answered quarterly and monthly. The enthusiasm that comes with the yearly training suggests that nurses are willing to pursue organized, bi-annual developmental opportunities, likely due to the limitations of high-load work, which create obstacles to regular training [2]. The 26.7% who chose as needed training means that they would like to be flexible to have the opportunity to fill a particular skill shortage based on the skills they need, including conflict resolution or strategy planning [8]. These findings suggest that there is a need to balance systematic training with convenient and focused training in order to support nurses in their busy

schedules and to encourage ongoing professional growth.

Figure 3: Preferred Development Types and Training Frequency

The Clinical Nursing Leadership Program is highly effective, as evidenced by strong satisfaction and career alignment. However, enhancing mentorship and shadowing opportunities and addressing workload barriers could further optimize its impact, ensuring nurses are well-equipped to lead in clinical settings [2].

Leadership Challenges and Barriers

In an interview with 13 respondents, qualitative responses revealed issues in translating program-learned skills, such as a lack of resources (e.g. staff shortages), barriers to career advancement, leadership of diverse groups, excessive workload, patient volume, fear of failure, and inability to collaborate. The systemic issue was observed as one respondent commented, Balancing Limited resources have been a problem in delivering patient care expectations [2].

In quantitative terms the High Workload barrier (69, 20/29) was the most important barrier, then Lack of Support (44.8, 13/29), Insufficient Resources (41.4, 12/29), Limited Mentorship (31, 9/29), Resistance to Change (31, 9/29), and Lack of Training (27.6, 8/29) (Al Sabei et al., 2023). A career progression was mentioned by one of the respondents as a reason. Such obstacles, especially workload and resources, restrict the impact of the program because they constrain the capacity of nurses to utilize leadership skills in practice [3].

Figure 4: Biggest Barriers to Effective Leadership

This bar chart illustrates that “High workload” (20 respondents) is the primary barrier, followed by “Lack of support” (13) and “Insufficient resources” (12), emphasizing systemic challenges. Notably, 100% (30/30) of respondents feel prepared for future leadership roles, indicating the program’s success in building confidence [9].

Career Aspirations and Program Support

A survey of 30 nurses at Prince Sultan Military Medical City indicated that most nurses had ambitious career goals and understand how the clinical nursing leadership program could help them reach such goals. The replies indicate that top leadership programs are strongly desired at the middle and senior leadership levels, and that specific demands are seen to support the program by mentoring, training, and career clearance [10]. The changes in nursing leadership with the organized development have been a valuable subject of the study, so these findings are not new [3]. A considerable percentage of the respondents indicated that they hoped to become high level leaders in five years. In particular, 56.7% (17 of 30) aspired to Nurse Manager, and 40% (12 of 30) wanted to become Directors of Nursing, meaning that the professionals sought positions at the middle and senior levels that could promote organizational and patient care outcomes. The less frequent aspirations were Clinical Educator (16.7%, 5 out of 30), Charge Nurse (6.7%, 2 out of 30), and Team Leader or “Any position (3.3%, 1 out of 30 each). The presented distribution reveals the existence of motivated nursing labor force, the aspirations of which are consistent with the strategic leadership roles, which requires the emergence of the higher-order decision-making and team leadership competences [1]. Nurse Manager and Director roles are popular, and it seems that the leadership program is building a vision of meaningful career growth, yet, in order to reach these objectives, strong support systems are necessary [11].

Figure 5: Leadership Role Aspirations within 5 Years

The qualitative responses of 21 respondents shed more light on the support that was required to make these aspirations a reality. The need to have a structured mentorship program, further training (clinical and leadership oriented), defined career prospects, and upper management backing were identified as central themes [12]. According to one of the respondents, the lack of career support would mean that I would not be able to develop based on my own will because structured mentorship and free-floating promotion criteria would encourage me to develop without fear [3]. This feeling is an indicator of a perceived lack of mentorship and clear promotion lines, which are essential when enabling nurses to take on a leadership role without fear. This mentoring requirement aligns with the body of literature that mentorship develops leadership skills in nursing practice, particularly high-stress clinical environments [3].

The best leadership program as described by 18 respondents is competency-based, healthcare-oriented, and oriented at practical skills training, shadowing, and mentorship. In particular, the respondents required training regarding such aspects of work as decision-making, conflict resolution, or transformational leadership, which are essential in team management and leading patient-oriented care [1]. This emphasis on shadowing suggests that experiential learning will be necessary to bridge the divide between theoretical and practical knowledge and enable the nurses to observe and replicate effective leadership behavior in practice [13]

Figure 6: Recommendation Rate

The high recommendation rate further indicates the impact of the program, 70% (21 out of 30) of respondents were Extremely likely to recommend the program, and 23.3% (7 out of 30) Likely, which translates to a 93.3% positive recommendation rate. The proportion of those who were neutral was only 6.7% (2 out of 30) and none stated that they would not

likely recommend the program. This strong score shows the program is effective in achieving career objectives, however the neutral responses refer to weaknesses areas, possibly because of the absence of mentorship or job orientation [1]. Increasing mentorship and clarity on promotion standards would also help the program to better serve the ambitious career ambitions of the nurses, which would secure a strong pipeline of leadership.

Discussion

According to the survey results of 30 nurses, the clinical nursing leadership has a substantial positive effect on the professional competence and leadership skills. Findings demonstrate high confidence and interpersonal skills, and career expectations align within the range which can be termed as a strong model of nurse leader development [14] However, the possibilities to reflect on the state of things and transform it with the assistance of the special interventions to make the program as effective as possible and to assist nurses achieve their dreams in a difficult medical environment could be included in the list of the systemic obstacles and gaps in the strategic skills [3].

One of the strengths of the Clinical Nursing Leadership Program is that it leads to high confidence among the members, with 86.7% (26 out of 30) of the nurses stating that they were either Very confident or Extremely confident in their team leadership skills. The latter illusion is also supported by the fact that all (100%) respondents agreed that they are ready to accept future leadership positions (e.g., Nurse Manager, 56.7, or Director of Nursing, 40 percent) [15]. This self-reported preparation proves that the program is fulfilling its mission of providing nurses with the sense of confidence to negotiate within the tangles of clinical leadership that is at the core of enhancing team performance and patient outcomes [3]. The focus on interpersonal competencies in the program, specifically on Communication, Team Management, and Problem-Solving (all mentioned by 90% (27 out of 30) of the respondents), is in line with the fundamentals of clinical leadership. The skills will also help nurses in managing multidisciplinary teams, conflict and evidence-based decision-making in high-stakes healthcare environments [1].

In addition to a high level of satisfaction, the program was rated as good or excellent by 93.3% (28 out of 30) of the respondents and 93.3% stated that it helped them to align their career goals. The results are comparable to the reports on the experiential learning the authors used the role of practicability of the contextual training in the development of nursing leadership [1]. The congruence and satisfaction of this magnitude suggests that this program is already geared towards the professional needs of nurses, largely,

nurses seeking mid and senior positions such as Nurse Manager and Director of Nursing [16]. The choice of the development approach, i.e., hands-on methods, i.e., Mentorship, and Workshops (73.3% each, 22 of 30), demonstrates that the program was effective in providing practical and nursing-focused training and that appealed to the practical needs of clinical leadership. It is also important that such alignment is grounded in the career goals because it will lead to increased motivation and commitment of nurses, improved retention and stability of the organization [3]. Despite these strengths, a wide gap in the strategic leadership competencies was identified in the survey, which specifically included Vision and Goal-Setting, rated as a strength by only 40% (12 out of 30) of the participants. This is a considerable gap, as the position of the Director of Nursing, with its strategic planning and organizational vision to undertake long-term healthcare delivery improvement [1], is a desired goal of 40 percent of nurses. The relatively low levels of these competencies suggest the possibility that the program may prioritize operational and interpersonal skills over strategic ones and, therefore, restrict nurses to top leadership roles. These gaps could be filled by offering a few workshops in planning, setting goals, so as to equip the program to train nurses to accept higher levels of positions as the need of the healthcare system evolves [1].

There are also systemic constraints that limit the effectiveness of the program, with 69 percent (20 out of 29) of those surveyed citing high workload as the biggest obstacle and insufficient resources (41.4, 12 out of 29). These obstacles, which reflect the issues of healthcare worldwide, do not provide nurses with an opportunity to demonstrate leadership in clinical practice [2]. To illustrate, qualitative responses suggested shortage of staffing and equipment and one nurse said, "Striking a balance with limited resources has been one of the challenges I have encountered in ensuring that delivery of patient care meets expectations. Both of these systemic issues reduce the viability of applying program-learned skills in practice and cause burnout and lower rates of leadership effectiveness, as workloads lack the time to implement or train strategic actions [2]. Career progression questions were also raised when the qualitative information also brought up the issue of the absence of promotion factors, and the top management endorsement empowerment [17].

The need in mentorship (73.3%) and workshop suggests that the program is successful regarding offering the appropriate training but still requires more practical opportunities. Qualitative responses repeatedly discussed mentorship, as nurses also questioned the importance of mentorship in developing confidence and practical skills. This respondent said, organized

mentorship and open promotion requirements would encourage me to develop with confidence [3]. The lower popularity of online courses (33.3, 10 of 30) suggests that nurses value interactive face-to-face education very much, which is likely justified by the fact that in a clinical setting, there is a need to receive feedback in real-time. Mentorship and shadowing must be used more frequently to fill the gap in learning and practice that already exists [3].

Although its 93.3% positive recommendation rate (70% Extremely likely, 23.3% Likely) indicates a strong impact of the program, the 6.7% (2 out of 30) rate of Very poor and the neutral recommendation response indicate that some gaps exist. They may be linked to inequality in exposure to training, inequality in resource distribution, or inequality in expectations between nurses with heavy workloads or who have limited mentoring access [2].

Limitations of the study should be mentioned should that 30 nurses sample will not suggest the diversity of the nursing workforce at Prince Sultan Military Medical City and therefore, the external validity of the findings may be restricted [18]. Lack of demographic information, including years of experience or position, prevents the analysis of the impact of these variables on the perception of the program [19]. In order to explain this fact, new nurses might have other priorities than old nurses and this information could be used and develop particular interventions [4]. In addition to this, self-reported data is associated with likelihood of inflation of self-confidence or even willfulness due to social desirability or objective assessment [4]. Future analysis would require bigger samples, demographics, and objective measurement including performance indicators to triangulate self-reports.

Recommendations

In order to increase the effect of the Saudi Tertiary Care Hospital leadership program, the following recommendations are suggested:

- **Expand Mentorship:** Expand mentorship initiative to match nurses with senior leaders to meet the need of 73.3% infused with the skill development [3].
- **Address Workload:** Hire or schedule to reduce the 69% workload barrier with the aim of overcoming the workload barrier [2].
- **Strategic Training:** Provide Vision and Goal-Setting workshops to fill the 40% competency gap [1].
- **Clear Career Pathways:** Establish clear promotion requirements to help in the vision of Nurse Manager and Director.
- **Flexible Training:** Continue to have annual training (66.7% choice) and have occasional sessions to train a particular skill.

Conclusion

The program of clinical leadership of nursing at Prince Sultan Military Medical City enhances professional competence and leadership skills of 30 surveyed nurses, as the confidence levels are high (86.7% Very or Extremely confident), interpersonal skills are high (90% report Communication, Team Management, and Problem-Solving) and career congruence is high (93.3% report congruence with goals) and the preference is to adopt the position of Nurse Manager (56.7%), or the position of a Director of Nursing (40). However, global healthcare vulnerabilities are reflected in system-wide limitations, particularly high workloads (69%), access to adequate resources (41.4%), which inhibit the use of skills and limit program impact [2]. The lack of strategic skills (such as Vision and Goal-Setting 40%), in turn, becomes an additional obstacle to high-level job preparation and requires training that concentrates on the specified skills [1]. The qualitative findings identified the following needs formalized mentorship (73.3%), and a visible career progression one of the interviewees said Structured mentorship and open promotion policies would be the driver of confidence [3]. High prevalence of recommendation (93.3% positive) but insignificant chasms (6.7% neutral items) support high value of the program as inequitable access or lack of resources. The program can maximize influence by encouraging mentorship, staffing to control workloads and career paths and improving the leadership pipeline and patient care. The future assessment should include demographic data and a larger sample size to address weaknesses in small sample size (30) and self-report error and provide further detailed plans on how to develop nursing leadership [4].

References

- [1] Rahimi RA, Oh GS. Rethinking the role of educators in the 21st century: navigating globalization, technology, and pandemics. *J Mark Anal.* 2024;12(2):182–197. doi:10.1057/s41270-024-00303-4.
- [2] Zaranko B, Sanford NJ, Kelly E, Rafferty AM, Bird J, Mercuri L, et al. Nurse staffing and inpatient mortality in the English National Health Service: a retrospective longitudinal study. *BMJ Qual Saf.* 2023 May;32(5):254–263. doi:10.1136/bmjqs-2022-015291.
- [3] Ystaas LMK, Nikitara M, Ghobrial S, Latzourakis E, Polychronis G, Constantinou CS. The impact of transformational leadership in the nursing work environment and patients' outcomes: a systematic review. *Nurs Rep.* 2023 Sep 11;13(3):1271–1290. doi:10.3390/nursrep13030108.
- [4] Smith JA. *Qualitative psychology: A practical guide to research methods.* 4th ed. London: SAGE Publications; 2024. Available from: <https://www.torrossa.com/en/resources/an/5730629>.
- [5] Wesolowski CT. *The Relationship of Authentic Leadership to Registered Nurse Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intention [dissertation].* Phoenix (AZ): Grand Canyon University; 2023. Available from: ProQuest OpenView: <https://search.proquest.com/openview/51e29631f393772fc3f94b1a8bbcb442/1?cbl=18750&diss=y>.
- [6] Pattison N, Corser R. Compassionate, collective or transformational nursing leadership to ensure fundamentals of care are achieved: A new challenge or non-sequitur? *J Adv Nurs.* 2023 Mar;79(3):942–950. doi:10.1111/jan.15202.
- [7] Gebreheat G, Teame H, Costa EI. The impact of transformational leadership style on nurses' job satisfaction: an integrative review. *SAGE Open Nurs.* 2023;9:23779608231197428. doi:10.1177/23779608231197428.
- [8] Bagwell GA, Cesario SK, Fraser D, Kenner C, Walker K. Breaking the cycle of nursing chaos: The need to address the nursing shortage. *Adv Neonatal Care.* 2023 Dec;23(6):495–498. doi:10.1097/ANC.0000000000001126.
- [9] De Brún A, McAuliffe E. "When there's collective leadership, there's the power to make changes": A realist evaluation of a collective leadership intervention (Co-Lead) in healthcare teams. *J Leadersh Organ Stud.* 2023;30(2):155–172. doi:10.1177/15480518221144895.
- [10] Pattali S, Sankar JP, Al Qahtani H, Menon N, Faizal S. Effect of leadership styles on turnover intention among staff nurses in private hospitals: the moderating effect of perceived organizational support. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2024;24(1):199. doi:10.1186/s12913-024-10674-0.
- [11] Al Sabei S, Ross AM, Al Yahyaei A, Labrague L, Al-Rwajfah O, Deterding K. Motivation to lead: a study of the supportive nursing leadership environment. *J Nurs Manag.* 2024;2024:2652746. doi:10.1155/2024/2652746.
- [12] Alzoubi MM, Al-Mugheed K, Oweidat I, Alrahbeni T, Alnaeem MM, Alabdullah AAS, et al. Moderating role of relationships between workloads, job burnout, turnover intention, and healthcare quality among nurses. *BMC Psychol.* 2024;12(1):495. doi:10.1186/s40359-024-01891-7.
- [13] Barros ACL, Menegaz JDC, Santos JLG, Polaro SHI, Trindade LDL, Meschial WC. Nursing care management concepts: scoping review. *Rev Bras Enferm.* 2023;76(1):e20220020. doi:10.1590/0034-7167-2022-0020.
- [14] Hassan EA, El-Ashry AM. Leading with AI in critical care nursing: challenges, opportunities, and the human factor. *BMC Nurs.* 2024;23(1):752. doi:10.1186/s12912-024-02363-4.
- [15] van Dongen L, Suidman L, Henriques MA, Jónsdóttir H, Leino-Kilpi H, Luderer C, et al. Improved

professional competencies and leadership in PhD-prepared nurses and doctoral students after participating in the cross-national and web-based Nurse-Lead program. *Nurs Outlook*. 2024 Mar-Apr;72(2):102144. doi:10.1016/j.outlook.2024.102144.

[16] Chavez EC, Jones TL, Yoder LH. Staff nurse and clinical manager perspectives of staff nurse clinical leadership: A qualitative descriptive study. *Advancing Medical-Surgical Nursing*. 2025;1(1):100005. doi:10.1016/j.amsn.2025.100005.

[17] Uluturk B, Yilmaz Altuntaş E, Hürmeriç P. Authentic leadership, motivating language, psychological empowerment, and work engagement: a serial mediation model. *Int J Bus Commun*. 2025;62(2):402–431. doi:10.1177/23294884231223521.

[18] Hult M, Terkamo-Moisio A, Kaakinen P, Karki S, Nurmeksela A, Palonen M, et al. Relationships between nursing leadership and organizational, staff and patient outcomes: A systematic review of reviews. *Nurs Open*. 2023;10(9):5920–5936. doi:10.1002/nop2.1876.

[19] Hoxha G, Simeli I, Theocharis D, Vasileiou A, Tsekouropoulos G. Sustainable healthcare quality and job satisfaction through organizational culture: Approaches and outcomes. *Sustainability*. 2024;16(9):3603. doi:10.3390/su16093603.

[20] Al Sabei S, AbuAlRub R, Al Yahyaei A, Al-Rawajfah OM, Labrague LJ, Burney IA, et al. The influence of nurse managers' authentic leadership style and work environment characteristics on job burnout among emergency nurses. *Int Emerg Nurs*. 2023 Sep;70:101321. doi:10.1016/j.ienj.2023.101321.

